

STEPS OF TEACHING STUDENTS TO CRITICAL THINKING BASED ON AN INDIVIDUAL APPROACH

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Abstract. *In the implementation of any research, the ideas, situations, theories and approaches that are chosen as the methodological basis of the research are considered to be one of the important features.*

The article describes the individual approach, the definition of the concept of individuality, and the stages of teaching students to think critically based on the individual approach.

Keywords: *mechanism, tool, individual approach, education, independent education, self-development, independence, problem, ability.*

The definition of the concept of an individual approach has its own content. By individual approach, we mean the establishment of a developmental educational field, and the recognition of the student's personality as the main criterion of the goal, subject, result and effectiveness of the educational system.

Individuality (Latin *individuum* - indivisible, breed) - represents the unrepeatable uniqueness of the psyche of each person who performs his activities as a subject of socio-historical cultural development. According to the researcher N.A. Muslimov, thoughts about the uniqueness of a person represent the external aspects of individuality. Man is a multifaceted being, in which physiological (body like other creatures) and social (personality) factors are embodied, but he also has original human qualities (individuality). Individuality is the distinction of a person from the animal and social world. The source of his life activity is embodied in the individuality of a person. A person with developed individuality fully relies on his own strength, and thus he appears as a free and independent person [1].

In the implementation of any research, the ideas, situations, theories and approaches that are chosen as the methodological basis of the research are considered to be one of the important features. This is a realistic approach, on the basis of which the theoretical idea that interprets the essence of the phenomenon under study is reflected, perceptions about the object are modeled, mechanisms, tools and conditions for its effective development are sought.

An individual approach to education includes:

- To see the student as a person, to develop his self-education, independent education, self-development, self-determination, independence and self-awareness, his ability to independently solve his professional and life tasks and internal personal problems.

- the student's needs, personal experience and actual level of development and construction of the educational process in the zone of his immediate development, that is, the personal direction of development; using the active content of teaching, focusing on positive assessment of students' achievements.

- Applying knowledge primarily as a means of personal development.

- Development of the universal cultural-historical abilities of the person, first of all mental, communicative, creative, reflexive, as well as development of the motivational - value sphere of the person.

- Implementation of subject-subject type of interaction in joint activity. The participation of two full-fledged persons in the educational process - the teacher and the student through their motives, goals of activity and abilities to implement it.

- Use in the main, effective, creative activity (reproductive activity aimed at developing a system of specific skills and qualifications serves as an auxiliary function in relation to the main activity).

- Involve each student in the process of active learning, not passive acquisition of knowledge, but active learning, practical application of acquired knowledge and clear understanding of where, how and for what purpose this knowledge can be used.

- The availability of free access to the necessary information to form an independent but reasonable opinion on a specific problem, not only in the information centers of one's own school, but also in scientific, cultural and information centers around the world, and the opportunity to study it comprehensively;

- Efforts to create conditions for students to constantly test their mental, physical, and spiritual strength, identify their existing problems and solve them together by performing various social roles.

- Active use of information technologies, as well as new pedagogical technologies, for example: collaborative learning; project method; multi-level education; portfolio; individual and differentiated approach in education, reflection.

Teaching students to think critically on the basis of an individual approach includes the following steps.

Stage 1. Evocation (EVOCATION)

Tasks: updating and summarizing the existing knowledge of the student on this topic: awakening interest in the studied topic; identifying and knowing the inadequacy of the activity.

At the challenge stage, work begins in the mode of problem-based learning. In classical pedagogical literature, the concept of "creating a learning motive" is used. At the same time, the technology of developing critical thinking offers various techniques and methods to implement this stage of work. A consistent system of methods includes both ways of organizing an individual approach and its combination with pair and group work. In the technology mode, the student at this stage already has his own goals and motivations for learning new things. It is an incentive to develop critical and creative thinking.

When students read a text (educational, scientific-popular, fiction), listen to the teacher's explanation, watch a movie, they try to hear the answers to the questions asked not by the teacher, but by themselves. The teacher can offer students to write with a pencil in the margin of the notebook while reading, to write in one column the key words that allow solving the contradictions that have arisen at that time, as well as key words that describe new information.

This can also be done while the teacher is explaining the topic. The questions raised by students are especially important. At the challenge stage, key words can be used to formulate them (what? why? how? what caused? etc.), and over time, students themselves will be able to formulate simple and complex questions without the help of the teacher.

Stage 2. Realization of meaning

Duties: active acquisition of new information; understand new information; connecting new information with own knowledge; observing the process of cognition and self-realization.

The stage of understanding is meaningful, at this stage the student directly works with the text, and the work becomes focused and meaningful. The learning process is always monitored along with the student's actions (marking, writing tables, keeping a diary), which allows you to monitor your understanding. The student will have the opportunity to think about the nature of the object being studied, because old and new information are interrelated, he will learn to formulate questions, define his own position.

Under the guidance of the teacher and with the help of his friends, the child answers the questions he asked in the first stage. Often, teachers who use technology to develop critical thinking in their work reduce the percentage of participation in the process of introducing students to new material. In addition, they offer students alternative sources of information.

Stage 3. Reflection (REFLECTION) - feedback.

Tasks: comprehensive understanding, assimilation and generalization of the received information, development of one's attitude to the studied material, identification of the unknown; analyze the process of learning the material, one's own mental operations; searching for topics and problems for further work ("new task").

The importance of the reflection stage: It is to bring the knowledge to the level of understanding and application. In the process of self-education, reflection occurs. Direct live exchange of ideas is important for developing communication skills. Expressing new information in one's own words allows it to be better understood and accepted.

Based on the individual approach, the model of teaching students to think critically, the student's professional formation is manifested by the expression of his unique characteristics in educational and pedagogical situations. In the educational process, the qualities related to mental, subject-practical and motivational factors are especially clearly manifested. At the same time, these factors also have many common aspects. As shown by the results of special research in this field, entry into professional activity, as well as a new position in society, is one of the emerging phenomena.

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